

Output-prediction Based Nonlinear Control of a Class of Neuro-musculoskeletal Systems

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Abstract—Motion control of neuro-musculoskeletal systems constitutes a challenging problem. The presented work proposes an approach exploiting the use of a prediction-based control technique to address some of the issues involved. In particular, the skeletal actuators (muscle-tendon complexes) are replaced with a virtual system, emulating the corresponding input/output behavior in the control design process. A control law, exploiting this predictor, prescribes the rate of change of system input (descending signals). It is shown to guarantee uniform ultimate boundedness of the tracking errors. To illustrate efficacy of the approach, the control law is applied to a simple two degree of freedom skeletal system, actuated by a set of five muscle-tendon complexes, activated by a simple neural model representative of a range of spinal functions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Advances in neurotechnology have enabled breakthroughs in the restoration of voluntary movement after traumatic spinal cord injury ([1–6]). Specifically, innovations in measuring and decoding intended movement from recorded brain signals ([3, 6, 7]) and development of patient-specific control technology ([4, 7, 8]) have allowed recovery of a high degree of autonomy in tetra- and para-plegic patients. In particular, patients with lumbar spinal cord injury can benefit from targeted Epidural Electrical Stimulation (EES) ([4–6]), allowing restoration of a degree of walking ability through stimulation of motor neuron pools ([4–6]). Stimulation patterns are designed to elicit ElectroMyoGraphic (EMG) activity profiles characteristic of sequences of human movement such as walking. EMG activity is continuously monitored and modulated in real-time, resulting in closed-loop control of voluntary movement. The control framework applied in [4–6] however brings limited attention to the neuromuscular dynamics supporting actuation of human legs in healthy patients. A key innovation in [4] lies in the ability to provide greater degrees of adaptation of stimuli patterns to patients, addressing issues stemming from inter-patient variability ([4, 5]). While the approach has produced outstanding results, improvements to the control design could enhance efficacy of the applied stimuli.

Advances in the corresponding control problem also support the emergence of novel avenues of investigation into the nervous system and the manner in which it controls movement. Consideration of functional constraints, emerging from interactions between nervous system and controlled

musculoskeletal system (an approach referred to as *embodiment*, or *physical grounding*) has proven to be of interest to neuroscientists ([9]), providing assistance in ascertaining merit of assumptions the developed functional models rely on. Additional informative constraints may emerge from consideration of the respective functional role (speculated in the neuroscience literature) played by distinct brain regions involved in motor control, and the manner in which they functionally interact ([10, 11]). A detailed understanding of mechanisms the brain relies on to enable the body to interact with its surroundings in a robust, mechanically compliant way remains beyond the grasp of modern neuroscience. Improving our understanding would benefit medical applications, as alluded to in the above. It could also prove useful in the design of artificial, intelligent agents. We pursue such advances through the development of control algorithms acting on a *neuro-musculoskeletal* system, building upon previous developments on control of musculoskeletal systems ([12]).

The problem is made more challenging by the fact that neural and muscle-tendon dynamics typically exhibit strongly nonlinear behaviors ([13–15]). Nonlinear control techniques can accordingly be expected to be of greater relevance than linear techniques such as e.g. Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) control ([16, 17]). A number of nonlinear approaches propose the use of neural networks to address this control problem ([18–21]). For instance, in [18, 19], the authors explore the use of a neural network to modulate the output of a pattern generator ([22]). This hierarchical construction, pairing pattern generation with top-down decisions, emulates a functional structure found in biological circuitry ([22]). Yet, relevance of the approach in [18, 19], to more complex musculoskeletal systems or control tasks remains unclear. Neural models also are commonly used in conjunction with reinforcement learning schemes ([20, 21]) to support digital modeling of human movement control. Careful design of reward functions allows to incentivize the neural controller to approximate principles of human movement, such as for instance minimal energy expenditure and human-like velocity profiles ([20]). However, such neural models typically fail to reflect most available system knowledge. A control design leveraging available system information, that is, some description of the spinal circuitry and musculoskeletal system acted upon, can be expected to provide better performance in the aforementioned EES use case ([4–6]).

Model-based control approaches exploit available system knowledge to inform control decisions. Such approaches ([12, 23–28]), using backstepping ([29, 30]) or model pre-

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dictive control ([31]), have been successfully applied to neuro-musculoskeletal systems in the past. However, model-based solutions proposed in [12, 23–26] do not robustly address system uncertainty. Such uncertainty is likely to be encountered when designing controllers to help restore voluntary movement in patients. Parameters characterizing the musculoskeletal model, in particular, are subject to substantial inter-subject variability. This issue of uncertainty is compounded by additional factors such as muscle fatigue and long-term changes in neural, muscle and bone tissue ([13]).

In the following, we build upon the result in [12], which provided a control law prescribing muscle fiber activation, guaranteeing stability of the origin of the tracking error system. Specifically, we consider the same class of musculoskeletal models, featuring a set of antagonistic Hill-type muscles ([32, 33]), but extend it to reflect a range of spinal dynamics. In the following, we design a prediction-based controller ([34–36]) relaxing a broad range of knowledge assumptions pertaining to the muscle-tendon model. The obtained control law prescribes descending signals ([37]) that support trajectory tracking in skeletal joint space. The two main contributions of the presented result are the following; (1) it exploits an output-prediction scheme to provide robustness to system uncertainty in the muscle-tendon model, and (2) it extends the result in [12] to account for a range of spinal structures, providing the first steps towards model-informed, personalized stimulation of motor neuron pools.

This paper is structured as follows. Section II describes the class of neuro-musculoskeletal models considered. Section III outlines the proposed control approach. The controller is applied to an example of neuro-musculoskeletal model featuring two skeletal joints, actuated by five muscle-tendon complexes in Section IV. Section V concludes this paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In the following, we consider a class of mechanical models representative of the skeletal dynamics of a set of human limbs. This skeletal model is actuated by a set of antagonistic muscle-tendon complexes, made to contract by a simplified model of spinal circuits. The skeletal system's state is described by n joint angles $\theta(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $t \geq 0$, and angle velocities $\dot{\theta}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$. Skeletal dynamics are described by

$$M(\theta(t))\ddot{\theta}(t) + C(\theta(t), \dot{\theta}(t)) + g(\theta(t)) = \tau(t),$$

$$\theta(0) = \theta_0, \quad \dot{\theta}(0) = \dot{\theta}_0, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (1)$$

where $M(\cdot) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $C(\cdot, \cdot)$, $g(\cdot)$, $\tau(\cdot) \in \mathbb{R}^n$. The muscle-tendon model is the following,

$$\dot{l}(t) = h(\theta(t), l(t), q(t)), \quad l(0) = l_0, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (2)$$

$$\tau(t) = \Omega(\theta(t))F\gamma_s(l(t)), \quad (3)$$

where $\Omega(\theta) \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $\gamma_s(\cdot) \in \mathbb{R}^{+m}$, $\epsilon_t(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{+m}$, $F \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, $l \in \mathbb{R}^{+m}$ and $q \in (0, 1]^m$. Specifics of the skeletal and muscle-tendon model are provided in [12]. Definition of the signals involved in (1)–(2) is provided in Section VI.

Expanding on the result in [12], we include a simplified model representative of part of the spinal cord's functional

behavior. The muscle fiber activation vector $q(t)$ describes the signal produced by the nervous system to elicit muscle contractions. This muscle fiber activation signal, and the corresponding motor neuron activation vectors, are obtained from the following relationships ([13]),

$$\dot{q}(t) = b^{-1}(q(t))(r(t) - q(t)), \quad q(0) = q_0, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{r}(t) = -r(t) + u(t), \quad r(0) = r_0, \quad (5)$$

where $r(t) \in (0, 1]^m$ describes motor neuron activation rate, $u(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ describes descending signals and $b(q(t)) \triangleq \text{diag}(\tau_a(p_5q(t) + p_4))$, $b(\cdot) \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, where $p_4, p_5 \in \mathbb{R}^+$ are characteristic parameters and $\tau_a \in \mathbb{R}^+$. Though (4)–(5) provides a rather simplistic representation of spinal dynamics, its inclusion allows to verify the ability of the proposed approach to support control of a dynamical system extending beyond just musculoskeletal dynamics (as in [12]).

Hereafter, we design a control law prescribing the rate of change of $u(t)$ using backstepping ([29, 30]).

III. CONTROL DESIGN

We build upon the approach in [12], defining the following skeletal tracking errors,

$$e_1(t) \triangleq \theta_d(t) - \theta(t), \quad t \geq 0, \quad (6)$$

$$e_2(t) \triangleq \dot{\theta}_d(t) - A_1 e_1(t) - \dot{\theta}(t), \quad (7)$$

where $\theta_d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ describes the set of desired joint trajectories. In addition, we define the following desired torque,

$$\tau_d(t) \triangleq C(\theta(t), \dot{\theta}(t)) + g(\theta(t)) + M(\theta(t))\left(\ddot{\theta}_d(t) + (P_2^{-1}P_1 + A_1^2)e_1(t) - (A_1 + A_2)e_2(t)\right), \quad (8)$$

where $A_1, A_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ are chosen Hurwitz, $P_1, P_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ are obtained from

$$A_1^T P_1 + P_1 A_1 = -Q_1, \quad A_2^T P_2 + P_2 A_2 = -Q_2 \quad (9)$$

where $Q_1, Q_2 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $Q_1, Q_2 > 0$. The torque profile in (8) is designed so that substituting $\tau_d(t)$ in (1) would ensure convergence of tracking errors (6)–(7) to the origin. In the following, we discuss the manner in which one is able to use muscle-tendon actuation to realize this desired torque profile.

In [12], we developed a model-based control law, relying on explicit knowledge of the muscle-tendon model. Here, we instead use the approach laid out in [34–36] to design a muscle fiber activation signal $q_d(t)$ guaranteeing asymptotic stability of the above errors, while requiring only limited information on the muscle model. We begin by deriving from (3) and (2) the following relationship,

$$\dot{\tau}_{fe}(t) = f(\theta(t), \dot{\theta}(t), l(t), q(t)), \quad \tau_{fe}(0) = \tau_{fe0}, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (10)$$

where $\tau_{fe}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$ denotes the joint efforts, separated into *flexor* and *extensor* contributions ([12]). We then design a predictive structure constructed to, for any admissible fiber contraction profile $q(t)$, predict the resulting torque generated $\tau_{fe}(t)$ with arbitrary accuracy. To that end, define the prediction error

$$e_p(t) \triangleq \tau_{fe}(t) - \hat{\tau}_{fe}(t), \quad (11)$$

where $e_p(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$. The following result, adapted from [34], describes the output predictor.

Theorem 1: Consider the following system,

$$\dot{\hat{\tau}}_{fe}(t) = \varphi(t) + \eta(t, \hat{\tau}_{fe}(t), \dot{\theta}(t)) + \gamma q(t), \quad \hat{\tau}_{fe}(0) = \hat{\tau}_{fe0}, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (12)$$

where $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}^{2n \times m}$ is chosen nonsingular, $\eta(\cdot) \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$ is a smooth function of its arguments, and

$$\varphi(t) \triangleq \frac{\tau_{fe}(t) - q_f(t) - \tau_f(t)}{\tau_1} - \beta_1 q_f(t) - \bar{A}_p e_p(t), \quad (13)$$

where $\bar{A}_p \triangleq (A_p - P_p/2) \in \mathbb{R}^{2n \times 2n}$, $A_p \in \mathbb{R}^{2n \times 2n}$ is chosen Hurwitz, $\tau_1, \beta_1 \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $P_p \in \mathbb{R}^{2n \times 2n}$ is obtained from $A_p^T P_p + P_p A_p = -(Q_p + I_{2n})$, $Q_p > 0$. The filtered input-output signals $q_f(t)$ and $\tau_f(t)$ are obtained from

$$\dot{q}_f(t) = -\beta_1 q_f + \eta(t, \hat{\tau}_{fe}(t), \dot{\theta}(t)) + \gamma q(t), \quad q_f(0) = q_{f0}, \quad (14)$$

$$\dot{\tau}_f(t) = \frac{\tau_{fe}(t) - q_f(t) - \tau_f(t)}{\tau_1}, \quad \tau_f(0) = \tau_{f0}. \quad (15)$$

Assuming sufficient smoothness of $\tau_{fe}(t)$, use of (12) to generate a predicted torque profile $\hat{\tau}_{fe}(t)$ ensures uniform ultimate boundedness ([38]) of the prediction error $e_p(t)$.

Proof: From the smoothness assumption, we infer existence of an upper bound for the higher-frequency filtering residue $\varepsilon(t) \triangleq \hat{\tau}_{fe}(t) - \dot{q}_f - \dot{\tau}_f(t)$. In particular there exists $\epsilon_p \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $\|\varepsilon(t)\| \leq \sqrt{\epsilon_p/2}$, $t \geq 0$.

Then, differentiating (11) over time we obtain

$$\dot{e}_p(t) = \bar{A}_p e_p(t) + \varepsilon(t), \quad t \geq 0. \quad (16)$$

Using $V_p(e_p) \triangleq e_p^T P_p e_p$, and differentiating along the trajectories of (16) over time, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_p(t) &= -e_p^T(t) \bar{Q}_p e_p(t) + 2e_p^T(t) P_p \varepsilon(t) \\ &\quad - e_p^T(t) P_p^2 e_p(t) \\ &\leq -e_p^T(t) \bar{Q}_p e_p(t) + \epsilon_p, \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where $\bar{Q}_p \triangleq Q_p + I_{2n}$. The inequality in (17) allows to conclude uniform ultimate boundedness of the prediction error $e_p(t)$ ([38]), with ultimate bound $\chi_p = \epsilon_p \lambda_{\max}(\bar{Q}_p^{-1} P_p)$. ■

The output predictor in (12) provides an advantageous (streamlined, uncertainty-free) approximation of the actual muscle-tendon model (3)–(2). In the following, we exploit this simplified representation within a backstepping procedure. In this perspective, we define the following backstepping errors,

$$e_3(t) \triangleq \tau_\mu(t) - \hat{\tau}_{fe}(t), \quad e_4(t) \triangleq q_d(t) - q(t), \quad t \geq 0, \quad (18)$$

$$e_5(t) \triangleq r_d(t) - r(t), \quad e_6(t) \triangleq z_{df}(t) - \dot{r}(t), \quad (19)$$

where $\tau_\mu(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$ denotes the vector of desired joint efforts separated into *flexor* and *extensor* contributions (see details provided in Section VI for the exact form of $\tau_\mu(t)$, the interested reader is further referred to [12] for a detailed discussion of muscle recruitment policy), $q_d(t), r_d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ denote the desired muscle fiber activation and motor neuron activation profiles, respectively. The filtered desired motor neuron activation rate $z_{df}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is obtained from the following relationship,

$$\dot{z}_{df}(t) = (z_d(t) - z_{df}(t))/\tau_z, \quad z_{df}(0) = z_{df0}, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (20)$$

where $z_d(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$ denotes the desired motor neuron activation rate and $\tau_z \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is a filtering constant. Smoothness of the underlying biological systems implies smoothness of

$z_d(t)$, which in turn implies boundedness of the filtering error associated with (20), $\varepsilon_r(t) \triangleq z_{df}(t) - z_d(t)$. Accordingly, one is able to find a fixed upper bound $\epsilon_r \in \mathbb{R}^+$ such that $\varepsilon_r(t) \leq \sqrt{\epsilon_r/2}$.

Form of the desired muscle fiber contraction, motor neuron activation and rate of change of neuron activation is derived from the definition of tracking errors, predictor (12), and neural model (4)–(5). In particular,

$$\begin{aligned} q_d(t) &= \gamma^{-1} \left(\dot{\tau}_\mu(t) - \varphi(t) - \eta(t, \hat{\tau}_{fe}(t), \dot{\theta}(t)) - \bar{A}_3 e_3(t) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + A_3 e_p(t) + \xi(\theta(t)) e_2(t) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

$$r_d(t) = q(t) + b(q(t)) \left(\dot{q}_d(t) - \bar{A}_4 e_4(t) - f_\alpha(t) \right), \quad (22)$$

$$\begin{aligned} z_d(t) &= \dot{q}(t) + \dot{b}(q(t)) \left(\dot{q}_d(t) - \bar{A}_4 e_4(t) \right) \\ &\quad + b(q(t)) \left(\ddot{q}_d(t) - \bar{A}_4 \dot{e}_4(t) \right) - f_\beta(t) \\ &\quad + P_5^{-1} P_4 b^T(q(t)) e_4(t) - \bar{A}_5 e_5(t), \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

where $\bar{A}_3 \triangleq A_3 - A_3 A_3^T P_3/2 - \gamma \gamma^T P_3/2$, $\bar{A}_4 \triangleq A_4 - P_4/2$, and $\bar{A}_5 \triangleq A_5 - P_5$, the error state matrices $A_3 \in \mathbb{R}^{2n \times 2n}$, $A_4, A_5 \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, are chosen Hurwitz, the matrices $P_3 \in \mathbb{R}^{2n \times 2n}$, $P_4, P_5 \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ are obtained from

$$A_i^T P_i + P_i A_i = -Q_i, \quad i = 3, 5, \quad (24)$$

$$A_4^T P_4 + P_4 A_4 = -(Q_4 + I_m), \quad (25)$$

where $Q_3 \in \mathbb{R}^{2n \times 2n}$, $Q_4, Q_5 \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ are positive definite. In addition, $\xi(\theta) \triangleq (P_3^{-1} \Delta^T P_2 + P_p^{-1} \Delta^T P_2) (M^{-1}(\theta))^T$, where Δ is defined in Section VI. Presence of $f_\alpha(t), f_\beta(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$, the form of which is provided in Section VI, emerges from the inclusion of filters in the control design, which allows to streamline derivation and mitigate impact of higher frequency signal components on closed-loop behavior. Note that, owing to smoothness assumptions, we are in practice always able to find $\epsilon_\alpha, \epsilon_\beta \in \mathbb{R}$, such that $\|f_\alpha(t)\| \leq \sqrt{\epsilon_\alpha/2}$ and $\|f_\beta(t)\| \leq \sqrt{\epsilon_\beta/2}$.

In the control design, use of the predicted torque $\hat{\tau}_{fe}(t)$, $t \geq 0$, in the stead of the actual value $\tau_{fe}(t)$, is accounted for by inclusion of $e_p(t)$ within the stability analysis. Impact on tracking performance is mitigated by extending the predictor structure as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(t) &= (\tau_{fe}(t) - q_f(t) - \tau_f(t))/\tau_1 - \beta_1 q_f(t) - \bar{A}_p e_p(t) \\ &\quad - \Gamma_p(t) e_2(t), \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

where $\Gamma_p(t) \triangleq P_p^{-1} \Delta^T P_2 (M^{-1}(\theta(t)))^T$.

Definition of tracking errors and virtual control inputs leads to the following error dynamics,

$$\dot{e}_p(t) = \bar{A}_p e_p(t) + \varepsilon(t) + \Gamma_p(t) e_2(t), \quad (27)$$

$$\dot{e}_3(t) = \bar{A}_3 e_3(t) - A_3 e_p(t) + \gamma e_4(t) - \Gamma_3(t) e_2(t), \quad (28)$$

$$\dot{e}_4(t) = \bar{A}_4 e_4(t) + b^{-1}(q(t)) e_5(t) + f_\alpha(t), \quad (29)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{e}_5(t) &= \bar{A}_5 e_5(t) - P_5^{-1} P_4 (b^{-1}(q(t)))^T e_4(t) + f_\beta(t) \\ &\quad + e_6(t) - \varepsilon_r(t), \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

where $\Gamma_3(t) \triangleq P_3^{-1} \Delta^T P_2 (M^{-1}(\theta(t)))^T$. Next, we present a control law, prescribing rate of change of descending signal, that allows to guarantee uniform ultimate boundedness of the error vector $e(t) \triangleq [e_1(t) \dots e_6(t) e_p(t)]^T$.

Theorem 2: Consider the neuro-musculoskeletal system composed of (1)–(5) and the following dynamic compensator,

$$\dot{u}(t) = \dot{z}_{df}(t) + \dot{r}(t) + P_6^{-1}P_5e_5(t) - A_6e_6(t), \quad u(0) = u_0, \quad (31)$$

where A_6 is Hurwitz, P_6 is obtained from $A_6^T P_6 + P_6 A_6 = -Q_6$, with Q_6 positive definite. Use of descending signal $u(t)$ obtained from (31) as input signal to system (1)–(5) guarantees uniform ultimate boundedness of the mixed tracking-prediction error vector $e(t)$.

Proof: The skeletal error dynamics are of the form

$$\dot{e}_1(t) = A_1 e_1(t) + e_2(t), \quad t \geq 0, \quad (32)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{e}_2(t) = & -P_2^{-1}P_1 e_1(t) + A_2 e_2(t) + M^{-1}(\theta(t))\Delta e_3(t) \\ & - M^{-1}(\theta(t))\Delta e_p(t). \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

In addition, with the appropriate substitutions, we obtain

$$\dot{e}_6(t) = A_6 e_6(t) - P_6^{-1}P_5 e_5(t). \quad (34)$$

Consider the Lyapunov function candidate

$$V(e) = e^T P e, \quad (35)$$

where P is the block diagonal matrix composed of the P_i 's (with $i = 1, \dots, 6$) and P_p . Differentiating (35) along the trajectories of (27)–(30), (32)–(34), yields

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}(t) = & -e^T(t)Qe(t) - e_3^T(t)P_3 A_3 A_3^T P_3 e_3(t) \\ & - e_3^T(t)P_3 \gamma \gamma^T P_3 e_3(t) - 2e_3^T(t)P_3 A_3 e_p(t) \\ & + 2e_3^T(t)P_3 \gamma e_4(t) - e_p^T(t)(P_p^2 + I_{2n})e_p(t) \\ & + 2e_p^T(t)P_p \varepsilon(t) - e_4^T(t)(P_4^2 + I_m)e_4(t) \\ & + 2e_4^T(t)P_4 f_\alpha(t) + 2e_5^T(t)P_5 f_\beta(t) \\ & - 2e_5^T(t)P_5^2 e_5(t) - 2e_5^T(t)P_5 \varepsilon_r(t) \\ \leq & -e^T(t)Qe(t) + \varepsilon, \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

where $\varepsilon \triangleq \varepsilon_p + \varepsilon_\alpha + \varepsilon_\beta + \varepsilon_r$, and Q is the block diagonal matrix composed of the Q_i 's and Q_p . It follows from (36) that $\dot{V}(t)$ remains strictly negative outside of the compact set $\mathcal{S} = \{e | e^T Q e \leq \varepsilon\}$, from which we conclude uniform ultimate boundedness of $e(t)$. ■

In the following Section, we apply the control algorithm from Theorem 2 to a simple model of upper limb, and present results from numerical simulation.

IV. NUMERICAL APPLICATION

We apply the proposed control approach to a two degree of freedom skeletal system actuated by a set of five muscle tendon complexes, representative of a simplified human upper limb constrained to move in the vertical plane; that is, the same musculoskeletal model as that considered in [12]. See Figure 1 for an overview of sign definitions for the two considered joint angles. In addition, we also include a simple representation of part of the neural dynamics afforded by the spinal cord, as discussed in Section II. This spinal model reflects that assumption that muscle fiber activation is driven by motor neuron activation. Motor neuron activation is, in turn, driven by a descending signal produced by brain regions supporting motor control. To illustrate efficacy of the proposed control approach, we investigate performance

Fig. 1: Skeletal system and joint angle definitions, reproduced from [12].

Fig. 2: Desired (green) and actual joint angle trajectories (shoulder joint in blue, elbow joint in red).

achieved using the predictor (12) and control law (31) when pursuing tracking of sinusoidal desired trajectories for both joint angles in the skeletal system shown in Figure 1. We simulate the closed-loop model in MATLAB, using ODE45 ([39]) for numerical integration. The desired trajectory is defined as $\theta_d(t) = a \sin(\omega t) + b$, $t \geq 0$, with $a = \pi/180 \text{ diag}([35 \ 8.75]) \text{ rad}$, $\omega = [3/\pi \ 4/\pi]^T \text{ rad/s}$, and $b = \pi/180 [52.5 \ 17.5]^T \text{ rad}$. Value of the control gains is as follows, $A_1 = 10 I_n$, $A_2 = 10 I_n$, $A_3 = 50 I_{2n}$, $A_p = 20 I_{2n}$, $A_4 = 20 I_m$, $A_5 = 20 I_m$ and $A_6 = 10 I_m$. In addition, $Q_1 = I_n$, $Q_2 = I_n$, $Q_3 = I_{2n}$, $Q_p = 10 I_{2n}$, $Q_4 = I_m$, $Q_5 = 10 I_m$ and $Q_6 = I_m$. Details of model (1)–(5), including value used for parameters, are provided in Section VI. Values used for the musculoskeletal model (1)–(3) are identical to those in [12], which were adapted from [13]. Initial conditions are chosen as follows, $\theta_0 = [0 \ 0]^T \text{ rad}$, $\dot{\theta}_0 = \dot{\theta}_d(0)$, $l_0 = [11.37 \ 13.64 \ 7.02 \ 6.53 \ 8.78]^T \text{ cm}$, $q_0 = [0.1763 \ 0.5514 \ 0.2597 \ 0.2701 \ 0.747]^T$, $r_0 = q_0$ and $u_0 = q_0$.

Tracking performance is excellent as shown in Figure 2, actual joint angles smoothly converging to the desired ones. The actual and desired torques $\tau_{fe}(t)$ and $\tau_\mu(t)$, separated into *flexor* and *extensor* contributions are shown in Figure 3. Flexors bear most of the effort, with extensors providing limited, near constant opposing torques (as determined by

Fig. 3: Desired (green) and actual torque profiles (flexors in purple and blue, extensors in red and orange).

the muscle recruitment policy, and cocontraction factor in particular, see Section VI and the discussion in [12]). The trajectory of muscle fiber activation and descending signals are shown in Figure 4. Descending signals typically display substantial oscillations in the transient, as shown in Figure 4 (bottom). Such behavior is related to initial slack in different parts of the system (in particular in tendons). The issue is mitigated by careful selection of initial conditions. Such an adjustment is not shown here, to provide of fairer representation of performance. In addition, the descending signal exhibits brief episodes of chattering. These are related to switching conditions (e.g. between muscle stretching and contracting regimes) in the muscle model from [13]. One may note the impact of system nonlinearities on signals, with muscle fiber activation profiles displaying non-trivial behaviors in contrast to better behaved torque profiles.

V. CONCLUSION

The presented work addresses the tracking control problem for a class of neuro-musculoskeletal systems. The approach uses backstepping and relies on the use of an output predictor [34–36] to relax most knowledge assumptions for the muscle model (streamlining representation of muscle dynamics in the design process). The approach, in addition to affording greater robustness to uncertainty, further expands upon the result in [12] by accounting for a simple spinal model. The control law was used to address the tracking problem for a two DoF model of an upper limb, actuated by a set of five muscles. Results of numerical simulations illustrate efficacy of the approach. Ongoing work is investigating the ability for the presented control approach to account for additional spinal pathways, extending the range of dynamics represented by (4)–(5). In particular, the control algorithm proposed allows to produce coherent descending signals supporting tracking in joint space. This constitutes a legitimately challenging control problem, for which existing alternatives from the neuroscience literature typically consider the use of large scale neural models, requiring substantial training to learn tracking for a given desired set of joint trajectories (see discussion in [40]). The approach presented here offers

Fig. 4: Muscle fiber activation (top) and descending signals (bottom) for each muscle-tendon complex.

an attractive alternative, requiring no training, and providing tracking performance for any admissible set of desired joint trajectories. The setup allows to investigate, in a closed-loop setting, the functional behavior of different spinal pathway models by extending the neural model in (4)–(5). Pathways investigated include those involved in presynaptic inhibition ([41]) and in the stretch reflex ([42]). The approach will help advance our understanding of such models, improving perspectives of embodiment for models of brain regions involved in motor loops ([43]), extending upon the notion of *physical* grounding of sensorimotor neural models (bringing to bear functional constraints tying the model to a representation of a physical reality) to pursue *dynamical* grounding (affording a richer set of constraints emerging from expected closed-loop dynamical behavior).

VI. APPENDIX

In the following, we provide the detail of the neuro-musculoskeletal model presented in Section II and used for simulation in Section IV. We also provide the specific form for a number of expressions used in control design.

A. Skeletal Model

The skeletal model in (1) is of the following form

$$M(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} (m_1 + m_2)l_1^2 & m_2l_1l_2 \cos(\theta_1 - \theta_2) \\ m_2l_2l_1 \cos(\theta_1 - \theta_2) & m_2l_2^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (37)$$

$$C(\theta, \dot{\theta}) = \begin{bmatrix} m_2l_1l_2 \sin(\theta_1 - \theta_2) \dot{\theta}_2^2 \\ -m_2l_2l_1 \sin(\theta_1 - \theta_2) \dot{\theta}_1^2 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (38)$$

$$g(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} (m_1 + m_2)l_1g \sin(\theta_1) & m_2l_2g \sin(\theta_2) \end{bmatrix}^T, \quad (39)$$

where $g = 9.81\text{m/s}^2$, and we used $m_1 = 1.86\text{kg}$, $m_2 = 1.53\text{kg}$ with lengths $l_1 = 0.29\text{m}$ and $l_2 = 0.24\text{m}$ (values adapted from [44]).

B. Muscle-Tendon Model

The muscle-tendon model used was adapted from [13], details are provided below for completeness. Tendon efforts are computed from the following series elastic gain,

$$\gamma_{si}(\epsilon_{ti}) = \begin{cases} p_1 (e^{p_2 \epsilon_{ti} / \epsilon_{th}} - 1) / (e^{p_2} - 1), & \epsilon_{ti} \leq \epsilon_{th}, \\ p_3 (\epsilon_{ti} - \epsilon_{th}) + p_1, & \epsilon_{ti} > \epsilon_{th}, \end{cases} \quad (40)$$

Muscle	F [N]	l_r [cm]	l_{t0} [cm]	α_r [deg]
Anterior Deltoid (DELTI)	1,218.9	9.76	9.3	22
Triceps long head (TRIlong)	501.7	13.4	14.3	12
Triceps lateral (TRIlal)	609.9	11.38	9.8	9
Triceps medial (TRImed)	932.7	11.38	9.08	9
Brachialis (BRA)	4,120.8	8.58	5.35	0

Tab. 1: Muscle-tendon model parameters.

where $\gamma_{si} \in \mathbb{R}^+$ represents the i^{th} entry of γ_s , $i = 1, \dots, m$, $p_1, p_2, p_3 \in \mathbb{R}^+$ are characteristic parameters (values used for simulation are provided in the next subsection), and $\epsilon_{\text{th}} \in \mathbb{R}^+$. Tendon strains are computed as follows,

$$\epsilon_{ti}(\theta, l_i) = \frac{\bar{l}_i(\theta) - l_i \cos(\alpha_i(l_i)) - l_{t0i}}{l_{t0i}}, \quad (41)$$

where $\bar{l}_i(\theta) \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $l_i \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $l_{t0i} \in \mathbb{R}^+$ represent the i^{th} entry in the corresponding vector, and $\alpha_i(l_i) \in \mathbb{R}^+$ is obtained from

$$\alpha_i(l_i) = \arccos \left(\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{l_{ri} \sin(\alpha_{ri})}{l_i} \right)^2} \right), \quad (42)$$

where $l_{ri} \in \mathbb{R}^+$. Value of $h(\cdot)$ in (2) is computed as follows,

$$h_i(t) \triangleq \begin{cases} \frac{(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 q_i(t))(\gamma_{ci}(t) - q_i(t)\gamma_{ai}(t))}{q_i(t)\gamma_{ai}(t) + \gamma_{ci}(t)/\alpha_3}, & \gamma_{ci}(t) \leq q_i(t)\gamma_{ai}(t), \\ \frac{\alpha_4(\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 q_i(t))(\gamma_{ci}(t) - q_i(t)\gamma_{ai}(t))}{\alpha_5 q_i(t)\gamma_{ai}(t) + \gamma_{ci}(t)}, & \gamma_{ci}(t) > q_i(t)\gamma_{ai}(t), \end{cases} \quad i = 1, \dots, m, \quad (43)$$

where $h_i(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ represents the i^{th} entry of $h(t)$, $\alpha_j \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $j = 1, \dots, 5$, are constant parameters, $q_i(t)$ represents the i^{th} entry of $q(t)$, and

$$\gamma_{pi}(l_{ni}) \triangleq \frac{e^{(l_{ni}-1)/\epsilon_{0m}} - 1}{e^k - 1}, \quad (44)$$

$$\gamma_{ai}(l_{ni}) \triangleq e^{-(l_{ni}-1)^2/g_s}, \quad (45)$$

$$\gamma_{ci}(\gamma_{si}, \gamma_{pi}, \alpha_i) \triangleq \frac{\gamma_{si}}{\cos(\alpha_i)} - \gamma_{pi}, \quad (46)$$

where $l_{ni} \triangleq l_i/l_{ri}$, $k, \epsilon_{0m}, g_s \in \mathbb{R}$ are constant parameters. $\Omega(\theta)$ in (3) is of the form

$$\Omega(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} \omega_{11}(\theta_1) & \omega_{12}(\theta_1) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \omega_{22}(\theta_2) & \omega_{23}(\theta_2) & \omega_{24}(\theta_2) & \omega_{25}(\theta_2) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (47)$$

where the specific expressions for ω_{ij} , $i = 1, 2$, $j = 1, \dots, 5$, can be found in [45].

C. Neuro-musculoskeletal Model Parameters

Parameter values used in (40) and (44)-(46) reflect those in [44] (itself adapted from [13]); $p_1 = 0.33$, $p_2 = 51.8749$, $p_3 = 3$, $\epsilon_{\text{th}} = 0.0201$, $\alpha_1 = 1/4$, $\alpha_2 = 3/4$, $\alpha_3 = 3/10$, $\alpha_4 = 0.0923$, $\alpha_5 = 1.8$, $\epsilon_{0m} = 6/10$, $k = 4$ and $g = 1/2$. Values for $\bar{l}(\theta)$ were obtained from [46]. Values for F , l_r , l_{t0} and α_r are provided in Table 1 (with values adapted from [46]). Parameters used in (4)-(5) are the following, $\tau_a = 0.01$, $p_4 = 0.5$ and $p_5 = 1.5$. Finally, the filtering constant in (20) is chosen as follows, $\tau_z = 0.05$.

D. Muscle Recruitment Policy

The vector of desired joint efforts, distinguishing *flexor* from *extensor* contributions ([12]), $\tau_\mu(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$ is provided by

$$\tau_\mu(t) \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \tau_d^+(t) + c(\tau_d(t)) \\ -\tau_d^-(t) + c(\tau_d(t)) \end{bmatrix}, \quad t \geq 0, \quad (48)$$

The cocontraction term $c_i(\tau_d(t)) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is computed as follows,

$$c_i(\tau_d(t)) \triangleq \frac{e^{(-\alpha_s|\tau_{di}(t)|)}}{2\alpha_s} + \beta_i, \quad i = 1, \dots, n, \quad (49)$$

where $c_i(t)$ is the i^{th} entry in $c(t)$. We used $\alpha_s = 0.5$, $\beta_1 = 3$, and $\beta_2 = 3.5$ for the elbow and shoulder joint, respectively. Finally,

$$\Delta = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (50)$$

E. Filter Residues

The form of $f_\alpha(t)$ is as follows,

$$f_\alpha(t) = \gamma^{-1} \left(g_\alpha(t) + (\bar{A}_p + A_3)\varepsilon(t) \right), \quad (51)$$

where

$$g_\alpha(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \nu_\alpha^+(t) + \frac{1}{2} \text{sgn}(\tau_d(t)) \nu_\alpha(t) e^{(-\alpha_s|\tau_d(t)|)} \\ -\nu_\alpha^-(t) + \frac{1}{2} \text{sgn}(\tau_d(t)) \nu_\alpha(t) e^{(-\alpha_s|\tau_d(t)|)} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (52)$$

$$\nu_\alpha(t) = M(\theta(t))(A_1 + A_2)M^{-1}(\theta(t))\varepsilon(t). \quad (53)$$

The expression for $f_\beta(t)$ is the following,

$$f_\beta(t) = b(q(t)) \left[\gamma^{-1} \left(g_\beta(t) + \bar{A}_3(A_3\varepsilon(t) - \gamma f_\alpha(\varepsilon(t))) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + \xi(\theta(t))P_2M^{-1}(\theta(t))\Delta\varepsilon(t) - \bar{A}_4f_\alpha(\varepsilon(t)) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + \left(\frac{\partial \hat{\tau}_{fe}}{\partial \hat{\tau}_{fe}} \bar{A}_p + A_3\bar{A}_p + \bar{A}_p^2 \right) \varepsilon(t) \right) \right], \quad (54)$$

where

$$g_\beta(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \nu_\beta^+(t) + \kappa(t) \\ -\nu_\beta^-(t) + \kappa(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (55)$$

with

$$\kappa(t) = \left(-\frac{1}{2} \text{sgn}(\tau_d(t)) \left(\nu_\beta(t) + \alpha_s \dot{\tau}_d(t) \text{sgn}(\tau_d(t)) \nu_\alpha(t) \right) \right. \\ \left. + \frac{3}{2} \alpha_s \text{sgn}(\tau_d(t))^2 \dot{\tau}_d(t) \nu_\alpha(t) \right) e^{-\alpha_s \|\tau_d(t)\|}, \quad (56)$$

$$\nu_\beta = M(\theta(t)) \left[-A_1(A_1 + A_2)M^{-1}\Delta\varepsilon(t) \right. \\ \left. - M^{-1}\Delta((A_3 + \bar{A}_p)\varepsilon(t) - \gamma f_\alpha(t)) \right. \\ \left. - \dot{M}^{-1}(\theta(t))\Delta\varepsilon(t) - A_2(A_2M^{-1}(\theta(t))\Delta\varepsilon(t) \right. \\ \left. + M^{-1}(\theta(t))\Delta((A_3 + \bar{A}_p)\varepsilon(t) - \gamma f_\alpha(t)) \right. \\ \left. - \dot{M}^{-1}(\theta(t))\Delta\varepsilon(t) \right) P_2^{-1}P_1M^{-1}(\theta(t))\Delta\varepsilon(t) \\ \left. + 2\dot{M}(\theta(t))(A_1 + A_2)M^{-1}(\theta(t))\Delta\varepsilon(t) \right] \quad (57)$$

F. Predictor

The predictor in (12) is parameterized as follows for the application considered in Section IV,

$$\gamma = \begin{bmatrix} 20 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -10 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -10 & -10 & 0 \\ 0 & -50 & 0 & 0 & 50 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (58)$$

and the function $\eta(t, \hat{\tau}_{fe}, \dot{\theta})$ is of the form $\eta(t, \hat{\tau}_{fe}, \dot{\theta}) = W_\eta \varphi(t, \hat{\tau}_{fe}, \dot{\theta})$, where entries of $\varphi(t, \hat{\tau}_{fe}, \dot{\theta}) \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 2n}$ are polynomials of input arguments (linear in $\dot{\theta}$ and $\hat{\tau}_{fe}$, product of $\dot{\theta}$ with $\hat{\tau}_{fe}$, and constant offset) and $W_\eta \in \mathbb{R}^{2n \times 4}$ denotes parameters obtained from Gaussian regression ([47]) using simulated trajectories as training data. Filter constants τ_1 and β_1 are set to 0.1 and 1, respectively.

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